

Donor Properties of 1-Amidino-O-alkylurea: Part XI. Dinitro Bis 1-Amidino-O-alkylurea Cobalt (III) Nitrite

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Synthesis and characterisation of dinitro bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(III)nitrite salts are reported. Aerial oxidation of cobalt(II) nitrate, 1-amidino-O-alkylurea sulphate and sodium nitrite in aqueous medium provides red coloured dinitro bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(III) nitrite. Isomeric compounds are also obtained by the reaction of 1-amidino-O-alkylurea sulphate on aqueous cobaltinitrite. Chemical, spectral and conductance studies are reported. These studies indicate that the first method leads to the trans dinitro complexes whereas the latter furnishes the cis series. The complexes isolated are cis and trans $[\text{Co}(\text{NO})_2(\text{AA})_2] \text{NO}_2\text{aq.}$, where AA represents the ligands 1-amidino-O-alkylureas, where alkyl groups are methyl, ethyl, isopropyl, n-butyl, isobutyl and isoamyl.

In the family of metal biguanide complexes or metal 1-amidino-O-alkylurea complexes, there is no report on dinitro derivatives¹. In the series of 1-amidino-O-alkylureas the cobaltic complexes that have so far been characterised, which contain two unidentate ligands along with the two chelate ligands are of the type²: $[\text{Co a}_2(\text{AA})_2]^{+n}$ where $\text{a}=\text{NH}_3$, pyridine, beta-picoline, acetonitrile or CN and AA=1-amidino-O-alkylureas. While working on the cobalt(III) complexes of the fascinating 1-amidino-O-alkylurea ligands we have sought to synthesize the dinitro derivatives and this paper reports the results of such successful studies.

Two general methods have been developed for such synthesis: (1) Aerial oxidation of cobalt(II) nitrate, 1-amidino-O-alkylurea sulphate and sodium nitrite in aqueous solution provides a red to orange red solution from which similarly coloured crystalline product gradually separates. No yellow bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(II) was detected, presumably because the pH could not be reached by the addition of sodium nitrite alone. The compounds have the general formula of dinitro bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt (III) nitrite hydrates. (2) The second general method that was found easily realisable was to warm an aqueous solution of sodium cobaltinitrite and the 1-amidino-O-alkylurea sulphate. Evolution of nitrous fumes occurs at room temperature which, however, intensifies on a steam bath. After filtration, crystalline brownish red coloured products separate, which also analysed as dinitro bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(III) nitrite.

A critical study of the preparations obtained by the two methods, allowed to discover some, though somewhat slight differences, in the properties of the complexes. We would now discuss them one after another.

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1. P. Rây, *Chem. Revs.*, 1961, **61**, 313.

2. R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, *this Journal*, this series, Parts IX & X.

(1) The dinitro bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) nitrite gives dark red, glistening crystals when obtained by the direct method of air oxidation, whereas the corresponding product obtained from sodium cobaltinitrite has a distinct brown red colour. Such sharp difference in colour however, could not be found in the products with the other substituted 1-amidino-O-alkylureas, though for both the series the colour varied between brick red to orange.

(2) The two series appear to have some slight difference in their solubility in water and in methanol and ethanol. In general this is our experience that the dinitro derivatives obtained by the cobaltinitrite method has a distinctly higher solubility in water as also in methanol and ethanol compared to the products prepared by the aerial oxidation method. As the chain length of the 1-amidino-O-alkylurea increases, the solubility in methanol and ethanol also increases and that again more prominent in the second series of syntheses. However, we would like to record that the overall solubility of both the series is appreciably low.

(3) The two series of preparations have often revealed some difference in their extent of hydration. Thus the complexes obtained by the first method sometimes crystallised with some water of hydration whereas those obtained by the second method show no water of crystallisation at all.

(4) The complexes being quite poorly soluble in water at ordinary temperature, we initially made some dilute solutions (0.01M) by warming for conductance measurements but discovered that the solutions have undergone very appreciable change in that these often recorded an abnormally high value for the conductance and the time of warming also appeared to have a pronounced influence on the conductance. In order to obviate these difficulties and uncertainties we then measured in methanol solutions, in which solvents, the solubilities are comparatively favourable and that, too, with the higher 1-amidino-O-alkylurea ligands alone. One interesting generalisation has come out of these studies. Whereas the Λ_M values for those complexes, obtained by the first method

TABLE I

Conductance studies at 31° in methanol

Complex	Dilution (litres)	500	1000	2000
1. cis[Co (NO ₂) ₂ (AP ⁱ UH) ₂] NO ₂	Λ_v			36.7
2. (a) cis [Co (NO ₂) ₂ (AB ⁿ UH) ₂] NO ₂		47.8	55.68	
(b) trans [Co (NO ₂) ₂ (AB ⁿ UH) ₂] NO ₂ .8H ₂ O				118.1
3. (a) cis [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AB ⁱ UH) ₂] NO ₂			55.68	
(b) trans [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AB ⁱ UH) ₂]NO ₂				118.1
4. (a) cis [Co (NO ₂) ₂ (AA ⁱ UH) ₂] NO ₂			55.0	
(b) trans [Co (NO ₂) ₂ (AA ⁱ UH) ₂] NO ₂ .2H ₂ O			91.7	121.4

APⁱUH=1-amidino-O-isopropylurea, ABⁱUH-1-amidino-O-isobutylurea;

ABⁿUH=1-amidino-O-n-butylurea and AAⁱUH=1-amidino-O-isoamylurea.

agree very closely with the expected values (around 90—105 Ω^{-1}) in such solvent^{3,4}, Λ_M 's for the complexes derived from the second approach are very much lower (around 37-55 Ω^{-1}). These appreciably lower values are indicative of strong ion-pair formation in

3. R. A. Krause and D. H. Busch, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 4830.

4. R. L. Dutta and S. Lahiry, *this Journal*, 1961, **38**, 689.

these systems leading to lower values. Many such examples have recently appeared in the literature, where extensive outer sphere ion-association has been taken to be the root cause of much low conductance values^{5,6}.

(5) Electronic absorption spectra of many of the complexes of the two series have been recorded over the wave length range 330 m μ to 560 m μ . The complexes all exhibit two absorption bands, one located around 335 m μ and the other around 440-480 m μ giving a broad absorption band. Whereas in both cases the bands were more or less over the same frequency region, we noticed one important generalisation that the complexes

TABLE II

Electronic absorption spectral studies

Complex	Band II		Band I	
	Wave number Cm ⁻¹	Molar absorbance litre mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Wave number cm ⁻¹	Molar absorbance litre mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
1. (a) cis [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AB ^u UH) ₂]NO ₂	30,000	6400	21,700— 21,300	430
(b) trans [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AB ^u UH) ₂] NO ₂ 8H ₂ O	„	6400	21,500— 21,300	452
2. (a) cis [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AB ⁱ UH) ₂] NO ₂	„	5660	22,700- 21,300	508
(b) trans [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AB ⁱ UH) ₂] NO ₂	„	4100	21,700- 21,300	336
3. (a) cis [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AA ⁱ UH) ₂]NO ₂	„	5640	22,700- 21,700	416
(b) trans [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AA ⁱ UH) ₂]NO ₂ 2H ₂ O	„	5560	21,700- 21,300	376

of the second origin have distinctly higher molar absorptivity than those obtained by the first route. In only one case the intensities have been found to be almost the same. The long wave length band represents the ¹T_{1g} ← ¹A_{1g} ligand field transition. The other ligand field band evidently is merged with other transitions in the system. This is suspected because of a very high molar absorptivity of charge transfer type. The spectral nature and the absorptivity are very much parallel to other dinitro cobalt(III) six co ordinate systems⁷.

(6) We have also investigated the infra red spectra of the red and brownish red varieties of dinitro bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) nitrite. Both the samples showed absence of any band around 1050 cm⁻¹. Both the samples however, showed the presence of strong bands around 810-830 cm⁻¹ but the red coloured compound obtained by the air oxidation method revealed only one strong absorption at 1315 cm⁻¹, whereas the other brownish red one revealed two bands located around 1310 cm⁻¹ and at 1335 cm⁻¹.

5. B. Bosnich, M. L. Tobe and G. A. Webb, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 1109.

6. S. Lenzer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, p-5768.

7. A number of such dinitro cobalt(III) complexes have been compared by F. Basolo in an excellent review in J. C. Bailar, 'Chemistry of Coordination Compounds,' Reinhold Publishing Corporation, 1956, p-338.

(7) Both the series of complexes are stable to heat at 120° and also on boiling in aqueous medium. There occurs no evolution of nitrous fumes. But on treatment with dilute HCl, there is evolution of nitrous fumes and reduction to cobalt(II) takes place.

The complexes being reported in this study may exist as geometrical isomers. We have therefore to examine critically the available information on these two series of complexes. In the case of a cis dinitro structure, the resulting complex will be asymmetric. This asymmetric configuration will in its turn, give rise to some special properties. We believe the synthesis by the cobaltinitrite method leads to the cis products whereas those by the general oxidation method in trans isomers. The extremely low conductivity observed in the case of one series is indicative of strong outer sphere interaction and such a situation is more likely for a cis rather than a trans derivative. Conductance has also been claimed as a tool to distinguish between geometrical isomers. Thus the cis $[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{NH}_3)_4]^{2+}$ shows a lower conductance than the trans species⁸.

FIG. 1 Electronic absorption spectra in methanol solution
1. cis $[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{AB}^1\text{UH})_2]\text{NO}_2$, 0.00025M.
2. trans $[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{AB}^1\text{UH})_2]\text{NO}_2$, 0.00025M.

8. M. M. Jones, "Elementary Coordination Chemistry", Prentice Hall, 1964, p-430.

The increased molar absorptivity of this same series over the other once again points to the same situation⁹. The cis complexes are expected to register higher intensity than the corresponding trans species. Finally the infra red spectra is revealing. Sharp infra red absorption occur around $810-830\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and around $1306-1320\text{ cm}^{-1}$ regions due to bending and asymmetric stretching modes of the NO_2^- group. A strong band around 1050 cm^{-1} is attributed to the nitrite asymmetric stretching vibration. Since none of the two complexes studied give any band around 1050 cm^{-1} we can safely conclude that the complexes involved are not nitrito species, i.e. the NO_2^- group is not linked to cobalt(III) through oxygen, it must be through the nitrogen. The red one showing one band in the 1300 cm^{-1} region and the brown-red giving two, safely classifies the air oxidation products as trans species and the products obtained by the cobaltinitrite method as cis derivatives¹⁰. The complexes obtained by the cobaltinitrite method have some slight higher solubility than those of the other series. Such solubility differences also point to a cis-trans isomerism in our system¹¹. Based on these evidences we assign the configurations to our complexes.

Trans series

(Obtained by aerial oxidation of Co(II) nitrate, 1-amidino-O-alkylurea and sodium nitrite)

Cis series

(Obtained by the action of 1-amidino-O-alkylurea on sodium cobaltinitrite)

This will not be unreasonable to mention other important dinitro Co(III) six coordinate complexes reported in the literature. Dinitro tetramine Co(III)¹² and dinitro bis propylenediamine Co (III)^{11, 13} have been identified as both cis and trans forms. The

9. (a) F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1962, p-730.
- (b) R. S. Drago, "Physical Methods Inorganic Chemistry" Reinhold Publishing Corporation, 1965, p. 176.
10. J. P. Faust and J. V. Quagliano, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 5346; B. M. Gatehouse, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, **8**, 79; J. Chatt *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, p-4073; M. LePostollec *et al.*, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, **60**, 1319.
11. (a) T. D. O'Brien, J. P. McReynolds and J. C. Bailar, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 749.
- (b) J. J. Sirola and R. O. Ragsdale, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 760.
12. W. G. Palmer, "Experimental Inorganic Chemistry", Cambridge University Press, 1959, p-537 & 547.
13. J. C. Bailar and J. P. McReynolds, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 3199.

dinitro bis ethylenediamines have also been obtained in two forms. The trans species has been prepared by air oxidation of a mixture of cobalt nitrate, ethylenediamine and sodium nitrite in presence of HNO_3 , whereas the cis product has been obtained by the action of ethylenediamine on $\text{K}_3[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]^{14}$. Similar action of glycine on $\text{K}_3[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$ has furnished the cis dinitro bis glycinato anion which has been resolved into optical antipodes via strychnine diastereoisomers¹⁵. The sodium cobaltinitrite method does not however, always leads to cis products, e.g. action of acetylacetonate on $\text{Na}_3[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$ has provided a trans dinitro bis acetylacetonato anion¹⁶. Dinitro bis O-phenanthroline $\text{Co}(\text{III})$ has also been reported recently¹⁷. Using triethylenetetramine, only the cis derivative has been located¹⁸. A similar action of a recently studied cyclic secondary amine has led to a trans dinitro species¹⁹. However, this last study appears to us to be sketchy.

We would have been happier if we could have succeeded in resolving the cis species. The poor solubility coupled with strong outer sphere association prevented isolation of any other salts, what so ever, far less with optically active anions.

In the light of the present studies, it appears that it might be possible to locate the dinitro bis biguanide cobalt(III) species by adopting some such similar procedures.*

EXPERIMENTAL

1-amidino-O-methylurea, 1-amidino-O-ethylurea, 1-amidino-O-n-butylurea, 1-amidino-O-isobutylurea and 1-amidino-O-isoamylurea sulphates were prepared and purified according to the published procedures^{20a}. Preparation of 1-amidino-O-isopropylurea sulphate was described earlier^{20b}. Sodium cobaltinitrite was prepared according to the method described elsewhere²¹.

cis-dinitro bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) nitrite.—Sodium cobaltinitrite (1 g) and 1-amidino-O-methylurea sulphate (0.9 g) were mixed with water (15 ml). Evolution of nitrous fumes was detected at room temperature. The resulting mixture was heated on a steam bath for about one hour until the evolution of nitrous fumes ceased. The colour of the solution changed from yellow to orange. The solution was then filtered and the

*Several synthetic routes were conceived for this purpose but no products of reasonable purity have been obtained so far (R. L. Dutta and I. Mallik, private communication). However, the routes described in this paper had not been attempted earlier and are currently being investigated by R. L. Dutta and K. K. Bhattacharyya.

14. E. P. Harbulk and M. J. Albinak, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 232; H. F. Holtzclaw, D. P. Sheety and B. D. McCarty, 'Inorganic Synthesis', Vol. IV, McGraw Hill Book Co., New York, 1953, p. 176.
15. T. J. Janjic, M. B. Celap and P. Spevak, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1963, **59**, 8340; M. B. Celap, D. J. Radanovic and T. J. Janjic, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 1494.
16. A. Rosenheim and Garfunkel, *Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 1865; L. J. Boucher and J. G. Bailar, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 1093.
17. D. M. Palade, *Chem. Abstr.*, **62**, 15736 e.
18. F. Basolo, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 2634.
19. B. Bosnich, C. K. Poon and M. L. Tobe, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 1102.
20. (a) R. L. Dutta and P. Rây, *this Journal*, 1959, **36**, 499.
(b) R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, *this Journal*, (in press).
21. W. G. Palmer, "Experimental Inorganic Chemistry," Cambridge University Press, 1959, p-549.

filtrate was cooled for an hour in an ice bath. The brownish-red crystals separated were recrystallised from hot water, washed with ice cold water and dried in air. The substance is sparingly soluble in water, methanol and ethanol. This has appreciable solubility in hot water.

trans-dinitro bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt (III) nitrite.—Co(NO₂)₂ (H₂O)(0.7 g) and 1-amidino-O-methylurea sulphate (0.9 g) were dissolved in water (15 ml), pH of the solution was adjusted to 7 with dilute NaOH. To this a solution of NaNO₂ (1 g) in water (5 ml) was added. A brisk current of air was passed through the resulting solution for one hour, during which dark red crystals separated. These were filtered, washed first with ice cold water, then with spirit and dried in air. The substance is sparingly soluble in water and insoluble in alcohol.

The other complexes were prepared by following a similar procedure as described for the methyl derivatives. These were all dried in air. The relevant analytical data are included in Table III.

TABLE III

Analysis and colour of dinitro cobalt(III) complexes

Complex	Colour	Co %	N %	H ₂ O† %
1. cis [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AMUH) ₂] NO ₂	Brownish red	Found: 13.8 Reqd: 13.6	35.5 35.8	—
2. trans [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AMUH) ₂] NO ₂	Dark red	Found: 13.6 Reqd: 13.6	35.8 35.8	—
3. cis [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AEUH) ₂] NO ₂	Brownish red	Found: 12.8 Reqd: 12.9	34.0 33.7	—
4. trans [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AEUH) ₂] NO ₂ H ₂ O	Orange	Found: 12.4 Reqd: 12.4	32.1 32.4	—
5. cis [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AP ⁱ UH) ₂] NO ₂	Brownish red	Found: 12.3 Reqd: 12.1	31.7 31.7	—
6. trans [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AP ⁱ UH) ₂] NO ₂ 2H ₂ O	Orange	Found: 11.5 Reqd: 11.3	29.3 29.5	7.0 6.9
7. cis [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AB ⁿ UH) ₂] NO ₂	Brownish red	Found: 11.7 Reqd: 11.5	29.9 30.0	—
8. trans [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AB ⁿ UH) ₂] NO ₂ 8H ₂ O	Orange	Found: 8.7 Reqd: 8.9	23.5 23.4	21.1 21.8
9. cis [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AB ⁱ UH) ₂] NO ₂	Brownish red	Found: 11.4 Reqd: 11.5	30.2 30.0	—
10. trans [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AB ⁱ UH) ₂] NO ₂	Orange	Found: 11.6 Reqd: 11.5	30.1 30.0	—
11. cis [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AA ⁱ UH) ₂] NO ₂	Brownish red	Found: 10.8 Reqd: 10.9	28.3 28.4	—
12. trans [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AA ⁱ UH) ₂] NO ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Orange	Found: 10.5 Reqd: 10.3	26.4 26.6	6.5 6.2

†By loss at 110°C.

The experimental procedure as described in Part IX was followed here.

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